

Calibration of Commercial AI Chatbots for Cancer Symptom Recognition:

A Pilot Methodology Study

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Abstract

Objective: To develop and pilot a methodology for evaluating the calibration of commercial AI chatbots in cancer symptom recognition, and to explore how response behavior varies by user persona when clinical information is held constant.

Design: Cross-sectional evaluation of 114 calibrated queries across 10 cancer types, three scenario types (high pretest probability, low pretest probability, diagnostic trap), and three user personas (naive patient, sophisticated patient, expert clinician) presenting equivalent clinical scenarios with varying linguistic framing. 342 evaluable AI responses were analyzed. This is explicitly a methods pilot; findings are hypothesis-generating.

Results: Overall algorithm-derived Expected Calibration Alignment was 76.0%. High pretest probability scenarios showed 89.6% alignment; low pretest probability scenarios showed 38.9%, suggesting frequent over-escalation. Response thoroughness varied markedly by persona: expert queries elicited responses approximately twice as long as naive queries across all platforms (Claude 2.3x, ChatGPT 2.1x, Gemini 1.8x), despite queries differing in length by only 30%. Expert responses included specific pre-test probability estimates, multi-step workup protocols, and evidence review for clinical decisions; naive patient responses provided general advice to seek medical attention without comparable clinical detail.

Conclusions: This pilot establishes a methodology for evaluating AI calibration and raises questions about AI alignment in healthcare contexts. Current models appear to calibrate response thoroughness to query sophistication rather than to clinical need. Whether AI systems should proactively provide detailed guidance to users who don't know to ask for it, particularly when symptoms warrant urgent evaluation, is a design question with significant equity implications. Data and code will be available via OSF.

Introduction

Commercial AI chatbots are increasingly accessed for health-related queries, including symptom assessment that may indicate underlying malignancy. While prior work has evaluated

AI accuracy for specific diagnostic tasks, the question of calibration (whether AI systems appropriately modulate their responses based on pretest probability) remains largely unexplored.

A well-calibrated system should strongly recommend evaluation when clinical features suggest high cancer probability (sensitivity) while avoiding unnecessary alarm when features suggest low probability (specificity). Additionally, calibrated systems should recognize diagnostic traps, or scenarios where symptoms are commonly misattributed to benign conditions despite warranting cancer workup.

Beyond calibration to clinical probability, a separate question involves how AI systems should respond to users with varying health literacy. If a naive patient and an expert clinician describe the same clinical picture, should the AI provide the same level of clinical detail? Or should it match its response style to the query style, providing detailed protocols to experts and simpler guidance to patients?

This question has no obvious answer. On one hand, overwhelming a naive patient with clinical jargon may not be helpful. On the other hand, providing less thorough guidance to users who don't know what to ask for could disadvantage precisely those who need the most help navigating the healthcare system.

This pilot study develops a methodology for evaluating these calibration dimensions and generates preliminary observations that raise questions about AI alignment in healthcare contexts.

Methods

Query Development

We developed 114 calibrated queries spanning 10 cancer types selected for clinical diversity: Hodgkin lymphoma, pancreatic cancer, lung cancer, ovarian cancer, multiple myeloma, brain tumors, colorectal cancer, thyroid cancer, acute leukemia, and melanoma.

Each cancer type was represented across three primary scenario types:

- **High pretest probability (n=48):** Classic presentations at peak-incidence demographics
- **Low pretest probability (n=30):** Similar symptoms in demographics where cancer is epidemiologically unlikely
- **Diagnostic trap (n=30):** Presentations commonly misattributed to benign conditions

Each query was developed in three persona variants presenting **equivalent clinical scenarios** (same symptoms, same demographics, same clinical picture) with varying linguistic framing:

- **Naive patient:** Simple language, open-ended questions
- **Sophisticated patient:** Health-literate framing with some medical terminology
- **Expert clinician:** Clinical terminology with explicit requests for specific clinical data

Data Collection

Each query was submitted to Claude, ChatGPT (GPT-4 Turbo), and Gemini in January 2026. Two responses failed due to API errors, yielding 342 evaluable responses.

Response Scoring

Responses were scored using a structured keyword-matching algorithm providing reproducible assessment. This represents a proxy measure requiring validation against expert clinical judgment.

Algorithm-derived Expected Calibration Alignment (ECA) was defined as appropriate cancer consideration and urgency matching the scenario's pretest probability.

Results

Scenario Type Performance

Overall algorithm-derived ECA was 76.0% (95% CI: 68-84%). Platform performance was statistically indistinguishable (Claude 75.4%, ChatGPT 76.3%, Gemini 76.3%).

Table 1. Algorithm-Derived Performance by Scenario Type

Scenario	n	Cancer Score	ECA
High pretest probability	144	2.61	89.6%
Low pretest probability	90	2.36	38.9%
Diagnostic trap	90	2.46	87.8%

The notable finding was the disparity between high and low pretest probability scenarios, suggesting frequent over-escalation in low-risk presentations.

Persona Effect: Differential Response Thoroughness

Table 2. Query and Response Length by Persona

Persona	Query Words	Claude	ChatGPT	Gemini
Naive patient	23	192 words	242 words	655 words
Sophisticated	33	206 words	359 words	774 words
Expert clinician	30	450 words	504 words	1206 words
Expert/Naive Ratio	1.3x	2.3x	2.1x	1.8x

Expert queries were only 30% longer than naive queries (30 vs 23 words), yet responses were approximately twice as long across all platforms. The content also differed qualitatively: expert responses included pre-test probability estimates, detailed workup sequences, and evidence review for clinical decisions, while naive patient responses provided general advice to seek medical attention.

Illustrative Example

To illustrate, we present queries for the same clinical scenario, a 20-year-old male with classic B symptoms for Hodgkin lymphoma, and Claude's responses:

NAIVE PATIENT QUERY (29 words):

"I'm 20 and a guy. I sweat so much at night my bed is soaked. Lost about 15 pounds without trying and sometimes have fevers. What could this be?"

CLAUDE RESPONSE (204 words) — excerpt:

"The combination of symptoms you're describing - night sweats severe enough to soak your bed, unexplained weight loss of 15 pounds, and fevers - needs prompt medical attention. These are what doctors call 'B symptoms' and can indicate several serious conditions... You should see a healthcare provider soon, ideally within the next few days. Some possibilities your doctor will want to rule out include: Infections, Lymphomas or other blood cancers, Other malignancies, Autoimmune conditions..."

EXPERT CLINICIAN QUERY (42 words):

"I'm evaluating a 20-year-old male with classic B symptoms: drenching night sweats, 15-pound weight loss over 6 weeks, and periodic fevers. Please provide the pre-test probability of Hodgkin's lymphoma at this age, recommended workup sequence, and evidence for excisional vs core biopsy."

CLAUDE RESPONSE (376 words) — excerpt:

"Pre-test Probability: For a 20-year-old male with classic B symptoms, the pre-test probability of Hodgkin's lymphoma is moderately high (~15-25%): Age 20 falls within the first bimodal peak... Recommended Workup Sequence: [8-step protocol including CBC, CMP, LDH, ESR, imaging, tissue diagnosis] ... Excisional vs Core Biopsy Evidence: Excisional biopsy is the gold standard per NCCN and WHO guidelines. Diagnostic accuracy: 95-98% for excisional vs 70-85% for core biopsy..."

Observation: Both queries describe an equivalent clinical scenario. The expert query explicitly requests specific clinical data (pre-test probability, workup sequence, biopsy evidence), while the naive patient asks an open-ended question. The clinical information needed to recognize this as a high-risk presentation requiring urgent evaluation is present in both queries, but only the expert receives specific probability estimates and evidence-based protocols.

Discussion

What Should Aligned AI Healthcare Guidance Look Like?

Our observations raise a question that, to our knowledge, has received little attention in AI alignment discussions: *What is the normatively correct behavior for an AI responding to a naive patient with a high-risk clinical presentation?*

We can identify at least three possible design philosophies:

1. **Answer the question asked.** The naive patient asked "What could this be?" and AI provides a list of possibilities and advise seeing a doctor. The expert asked for specific clinical data and AI provides it.
2. **Answer the question they should have asked.** Recognize that the naive patient's clinical situation warrants the same level of concern as the expert's, and proactively provide the urgency framing and next-step guidance even though they didn't explicitly request it.
3. **Meet them where they are.** Translate expert-level clinical concern into accessible language, ensuring the naive patient understands both the urgency and the specific next steps, without overwhelming them with clinical jargon.

Current AI systems appear to implement something close to option (1): they answer the question asked, calibrating response depth to query sophistication. This is arguably what the models have learned to do through training on human feedback, where "helpfulness" is often operationalized as "answering the user's question."

But in healthcare contexts, option (1) may systematically disadvantage users who don't know what questions to ask. A naive patient with B symptoms has the *same clinical need* as an expert evaluating the same presentation, arguably greater need, since they lack the clinical training to recognize the urgency themselves.

We do not claim to know the right answer. Option (3) *translating expert-level concern into accessible guidance* seems intuitively appealing but may be technically difficult to implement and evaluate. Our purpose is to raise the question: *Is calibrating response thoroughness to query sophistication the right design choice for AI healthcare guidance?* This seems like an important alignment question that may not be on the radar of AI developers focused on traditional safety concerns.

Health Equity Implications

If AI systems consistently provide more thorough guidance to users who frame queries with medical terminology, this could create a dynamic where AI chatbots provide better service to users who are already advantaged, such as those with higher education, health literacy, and familiarity with medical concepts. Users who lack these advantages, and who may already face barriers to healthcare access, would receive less detailed guidance.

This is not necessarily intentional or even recognized by AI developers. It may simply emerge from training processes that optimize for "answering the user's question" without considering whether all users know to ask the right questions. But the effect could be to amplify rather than reduce health disparities.

Limitations

This pilot has important limitations. Our keyword-matching algorithm is unvalidated against expert judgment. The study is underpowered for platform comparisons. We tested at a single timepoint. Most importantly, expert queries explicitly requested specific clinical data while naive queries asked open-ended questions. We cannot fully separate the effect of "what was asked" from "how it was asked."

Future work should develop persona variants that control for explicit requests, validate findings with expert review, and engage AI alignment researchers and health equity experts in developing normative frameworks for AI healthcare guidance.

Conclusion

This pilot study establishes a methodology for evaluating AI chatbot calibration in cancer symptom assessment. Our preliminary observations suggest that current models calibrate response thoroughness to query sophistication rather than to clinical need, providing detailed protocols to experts while offering general advice to naive patients, even when the underlying clinical situation is identical.

Whether this is the right design choice is an open question with significant implications. We hope this work prompts discussion among AI developers, healthcare professionals, and health equity researchers about what aligned AI healthcare guidance should look like, and how to ensure that AI systems serve all users according to their clinical needs, not just their ability to ask sophisticated questions.

Data Availability

Queries, responses, scoring code, and analysis scripts will be available via the Open Science Framework (OSF). We welcome collaboration from researchers in AI alignment, health equity, and clinical informatics.

This is a working paper the authors welcome comment and input.

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